

Two-Stage Scheme for Geolocation using Mobile Sensor Networks with Optimal Formations

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Abstract—Recent advancements in low power micro sensors and wireless network technology have enabled a host of new sensor network applications. One such application is collaborative geolocation using time difference of arrival measurements from a wireless sensor network consisting of mobile ground or airborne sensor nodes. This paper introduces a two-stage geolocation scheme that begins in an optimal bearing estimate formation and then reconfigures to a formation that yields an optimal position estimate. Using optimal sensor formations for bearing and position estimates, enables a network to obtain an optimal estimate of a target emitter's position. Through simulation the performance of such a scheme is analyzed and compared to that of a random fixed array. Its implementation on an airborne quadrotor network is also explored and is shown to be viable despite the network's unsteady node station keeping.

Keywords—Two-stage geolocation, TDOA, MLE, and mobile wireless sensor network

I. INTRODUCTION

Time difference of arrival (TDOA) is an effective technique for the passive geolocation of a wireless emitter [1]-[3]. Through the use of dispersed sensor nodes that collect a target's wireless signal's time of arrival data, the target's location is estimated. Recent advancements in low power micro sensors and wireless network technology have enabled the implementation of such a technique on a network of small mobile nodes. One such implementation is the formation of a wireless sensor network (WSN) from a group of mobile sensor nodes. This network is able to reconfigure itself to any desired formation. This capability gives the control over the sensor-emitter geometry, which plays a major part in determining the accuracy of a maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). The relationship between sensor-emitter geometry and estimator accuracy is called geometric dilution of precision [2]. While this body of research can be used with generic mobile nodes, it is intended for mobile WSNs that can relocate and hold a given position. These networks can consist of unmanned ground vehicle nodes [4] and/or unmanned aerial vehicle nodes [5]. Of particular interest are semi-stationary airborne networks consisting of multirotor aerial vehicles [5]. These airborne networks are highly mobile, providing an advantageous vantage point that ensures line-of-sight (LOS) signal paths, and can operate at an altitude above the noisy surface environment. For this reason, the airborne WSN will be the target network for this research.

This paper introduces a reconfigurable two-stage geolocation scheme that utilizes the optimal node formations derived by Ho and Vicente [1]. By using reconfigurable sensor

nodes we show that a high precision geolocation estimate can be obtained. Through analysis and simulation we investigate the performance of the two-stage scheme and evaluate the viability of its implementation on a WSN consisting of quadrotors. The overall system concept is illustrated in Fig. 1. This system will have a robust LOS path to the target transmitters and can support a host of remote sensing applications beyond geolocation.

A. Unmanned Systems for Mobile Wireless Sensor Networks

An unmanned multirotor system is built on modern technology yet remains a relatively simple machine. For instance, a quadrotor has four rotors held together with a rigid cross frame [5], [6]. Control is accomplished through the manipulation of each rotor's thrust. The system is under actuated, with the remaining degrees of freedom handled through system dynamics. Having demonstrated their effectiveness in many applications such as 3-D environment mapping, transportation, and construction, they have become a popular research platform and an ideal platform for remote sensing applications. For more information regarding multirotor aerial vehicles see [5], [7].

Unmanned ground vehicles have been proven useful in sensor network applications such as search and rescue and disaster response [8], [9]. Typically ground vehicles consist of a suite of sensors mounted on a wheeled vehicle. They too are relatively simple machines with system dynamics similar to multirotor systems [4].

II. OPTIMAL FORMATIONS FOR MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION

It is important to note that the analysis and simulations in this paper will be limited to a 2D scenario, as to better explain

Fig. 1. Geolocation from a mobile WSN.

and illustrate each concept. The extension into 3D scenarios is straight forward but needlessly complicated and thus not the focus of this paper.

A. Maximum Likelihood Estimation with Time Difference of Arrival measurements

The TDOA technique is based on a relatively simple concept. An emitter transmits a signal or electromagnetic pulse at time t_0 , as the signal arrives at each sensor node a time of arrival is measured and is given by

$$t_i = t_0 + \frac{D_i}{c}, \quad (1)$$

where t_i , D_i , and c are the time of arrival at the i th node, distance from emitter to i th node, and the speed of light, respectively. By taking the difference between two node's times of arrival, t_0 can be eliminated. This puts the TDOA equation in the form of

$$t_2 - t_1 = \frac{D_2 - D_1}{c}. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is rewritten to include the emitter's position as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{r_1^2 + r_e^2 - 2r_1r_e \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_e)} \\ & - \sqrt{r_2^2 + r_e^2 - 2r_2r_e \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_e)} = c(t_2 - t_1), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where (r_e, θ_e) is the emitter's position in polar coordinates. With three sensor nodes yielding two simultaneous equations in the form of (3), the location of the emitter can be resolved. For a closed form solution of the TDOA equations see [10].

One possible method for the estimation of an emitter's location using TDOA measurements is the iterative MLE. From [2] a MLE is derived using the Taylor-series expansion method. Here the MLE linearizes the TDOA equations in order to provide an asymptotically optimal estimate based on a set of simultaneous TDOA measurements. This is assuming that the measurement errors are zero mean and Gaussian distributed. In [2] the MLE of the emitter's position vector \hat{R} with its corresponding covariance matrix is

$$\hat{R} = R_0 + c(H^T G^T N^{-1} G H)^{-1} H^T G^T N^{-1} (G t - G D_0 / c) \quad (4)$$

$$P = c^2 (H^T G^T N^{-1} G H)^{-1}, \quad (5)$$

where for the case of $M = 4$ nodes, R_0 is an initial guess,

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

and,

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{r_i - r_0 \cos(\theta_i - \theta_0)}{D_{0i}} & \frac{r_i r_0 \sin(\theta_i - \theta_0)}{D_{0i}} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{r_M - r_0 \cos(\theta_M - \theta_0)}{D_{0i}} & \frac{r_M r_0 \sin(\theta_M - \theta_0)}{D_{0i}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

In (7), (r_0, θ_0) , (r_i, θ_i) , and D_{0i} are the initial guess range and bearing, i th node range and bearing, and the distance between the initial guess and the i th node, respectively. In (4)

$$N = G N_\epsilon G^T, \quad (8)$$

where N_ϵ is the covariance matrix for the arrival time errors, and

$$t = t_0 \mathbf{1} + \frac{D}{c} + \epsilon, \quad (9)$$

Where $\mathbf{1}$, D , and ϵ are a unity column vector of length M , a column vector containing D_{0i} , and a column vector containing the arrival time measurement errors, respectively.

B. Optimal Sensor Node Formations for Range and Bearing Estimates

In TDOA geolocation estimation, it is known that accuracy is dependent to varying degrees on measurement precision, sensor quantity and sensor arrangement [1]. In [1], Ho and Vicente developed the optimum sensor formations for the case where range and bearing estimates are decoupled. This optimal formation is found to be a set of concentric circles consisting of subgroups of sensors equally spaced along the circumference. These formations are derived from optimizing the minimum estimation variance from the Cramer-Rao lower bound (CRLB) of an unbiased estimator with Gaussian noise. Additionally, it is assumed that the estimation is done via MLE and sensor deployment is confined to a circular area.

From [1], the Fisher information matrix for the estimation of an emitter's position u in polar coordinates (r, θ) is found to be

$$F(u) = \begin{bmatrix} X & Y \\ Y & Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial d^0}{\partial r} & \frac{\partial d^0}{\partial \theta} \end{bmatrix}^T Q_d^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial d^0}{\partial r} & \frac{\partial d^0}{\partial \theta} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where d, r, θ , and Q_d are the TDOA measurement vector, range, bearing, and covariance matrix of the noise vector, respectively. X, Y , and Z are found to be

$$X = \frac{2}{\sigma_d^2 M} \left(\frac{1}{2cr^2} \right)^2 \{ M \sum_{i=1}^M l_i^4 \sin^4(\theta - \phi_i) - [\sum_{i=1}^M l_i^2 \sin^2(\theta - \phi_i)]^2 \}, \quad (11)$$

$$Y = \frac{2}{\sigma_d^2 M} \left(\frac{-1}{2c^2 r^2} \right) \{ M \sum_{i=1}^M l_i^3 \sin^3(\theta - \phi_i) - [\sum_{i=1}^M l_i^2 \sin^2(\theta - \phi_i)] [\sum_{i=1}^M l_i \sin(\theta - \phi_i)] \}, \quad (12)$$

$$Z = \frac{2}{\sigma_d^2 M} \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \right) \{ M \sum_{i=1}^M l_i^2 \sin^2(\theta - \phi_i) - [\sum_{i=1}^M l_i \sin(\theta - \phi_i)]^2 \}, \quad (13)$$

where σ_d^2 , l_i , and ϕ_i are the noise variance, distance of i th sensor from origin, and angle of i th sensor with respect to the y -axis, respectively. In order to decouple the range and bearing estimates Y must equal zero. With close examination of (12), it is shown that a sensor formation of concentric circles with equally spaced sensor satisfies this requirement. With range

and bearing decoupled, the CRLB for range and bearing become

$$r_{CRLB} = \frac{1}{\bar{X}}, \quad \theta_{CRLB} = \frac{1}{\bar{Z}}. \quad (14)$$

The optimal formations for range/position and bearing are then derived by maximizing X and Z and are illustrated in Fig. 2 and 3. Note that in [1] it is shown that the formation for range and position estimates are approximately equivalent. From [1] the CRLB of the two most pertinent formations, the circular bearing and linear range is

$$\theta_{CRLB} = \left[\frac{1}{c^2 \sigma_d^2} \left(\frac{L}{2} \right)^2 M \right]^{-1}. \quad (15)$$

$$r_{CRLB} = \left[\frac{1}{\sigma_d^2} \left(\frac{1}{cr^2} \right)^2 \sin^4 \theta \left(\frac{L}{2} \right)^4 \frac{M}{8} \right]^{-1}, \quad (16)$$

where L is the diameter of the deployment area. For more details regarding these optimal formations please refer to [1].

III. TWO STAGE GEOLOCATION SCHEME

Under the assumption that the sensor deployment area is confined to a circular area of diameter L , the two stage MLE geolocation scheme provides an optimal estimation of a target emitter's location.

The optimal formation's accuracy is found to be dependent on a number of parameters. With this in mind, the most accurate range and position estimates are obtained using a linear formation but with a caveat. The accuracy of this formation is dependent on the emitters bearing angle θ , and is optimal only when the emitter is normal to the linear

Fig. 2. Optimal sensor formation for range and position estimates.

Fig. 3. Optimal sensor formation for bearing estimates.

formation. In order to use the optimal linear formation, the emitters bearing must first be obtained. The two-staged scheme meets this requirement by using a circular formation in the first stage to obtain an optimal bearing estimate. Even though the circular formation is not optimal for position estimates, its bearing estimate does not depend on the bearing angle. The bearing information is then used to form the optimal linear formation in the correct orientation.

A. System Configuration and Operations

The two-stage geolocation scheme in Fig. 4 and 5 is shown with $M = 8$. More sensors can be added according to Fig. 2 and 3 for increased accuracy. The scheme begins with eight nodes equally spaced around a circle of diameter L , centered about the origin.

In the first stage (Fig. 4), the sensors are arranged in the circular pattern yielding an optimal bearing estimate. This estimate is independent of the bearing angle and allows the system to form its second formation in the second stage. In the second stage (Fig. 5), each node moves from its position in the circular formation to form the linear range/position estimate formation using the bearing estimate from the first stage. This is done by forming a line centered on the origin and perpendicular to the bearing angle obtained in the first stage. This formation has three groups of nodes positioned closely together (half wavelength). These three groups form a linear formation centered on the origin as shown in Fig. 2. The two outer groups contain two nodes each, while the center group has four. The two nodes closest to each outer group position will move to form that node group. The remaining four nodes then move to the origin to form the center group. With the formation now in a linear formation perpendicular to the emitter, an optimal range/position estimate is obtained.

IV. SIMULATIONS

In this section, the effectiveness of the two-stage geolocation scheme is presented through simulations. For each

Fig. 4. Stage one formation with $M = 8$, single sensor node (dot) and target emitter (star).

Fig. 5. Stage two formation with $M = 8$, two node sensor group (circle), four node sensor group (diamond), and target emitter (star).

simulation the number of sensors used is eight, and their deployment is limited to a 100 meters radius circular area centered about the origin. Unless otherwise stated, the noise power is set to $(10^{-10})^2$, and the target emitter is set to a range of 1000 meters. The MLE estimator using the Taylor series expansion method from [2] is used in all simulations. This simulation also assumes that all nodes are synchronized in time and each sensor's position information is known.

A. Two-Stage Geolocation Scheme Accuracy

In this simulation the mean square error (MSE) of the position estimate from the two stage case is compared to the fixed linear and circular formation. The network is deployed about the origin as seen in Fig. 2 and 3. Here the MLE is used with 10000 iterations. The target emitter is at a range of 1000 meters with bearing angle set between $-\pi/2$ and $\pi/2$. Demonstrative of (15) and (16), Fig. 6 shows the resulting MSE of each case at different bearing angles. It is evident that the accuracy of the fixed linear formation is strongly dependent on the emitter bearing angle θ , with optimal performance when the target is normal to the formation. As indicated by (15) the fixed circular formation performance is independent of θ . Since the two-stage scheme always forms the linear formation perpendicular to it in the second stage, the optimal performance of the fixed linear formation is obtain independent of the bearing angle. This is the key benefit of the two-stage scheme.

Regarding the optimality of the two-stage scheme, it is important to compare its performance with that of a random formation under the same constraints. Fig. 7 and 8 are resultant from two simulations focused on estimator accuracy at different bearing angles and TDOA noise power levels. Here, the random fixed formation comprised of a uniformly distributed formation within a circular area of diameter L . The MSE for the random formation is based on the ensemble average of 1000 trails. As indicated in Fig. 7 and 8, the two-stage scheme shows universal improvement in performance compared to the random fixed formation.

Fig. 6. Accuracy of position estimate for fixed linear formation (solid line), fixed circular formation (cross symbol), and two-staged scheme (circle symbol).

Fig. 7. Comparison of the two-stage scheme (circles symbol) and random fixed formation (cross symbol).

Fig. 8. Accuracy of position estimate for the two-stage scheme (solid line) and random fixed formation (dotted line) versus TDOA noise power.

B. Effects of Unsteady Station Keeping in an Quadrotor Sensor Network

Of interest to this paper is the implementation of the two-stage scheme on an airborne network consisting of quadrotor sensor nodes. This network possesses a high degree of mobility, making it perfect for the two-stage scheme. Assuming that each quadrotor node knows its true position, the problem of its unsteady station keeping must be addressed. This unsteadiness is mainly due to wind and causes nodes to momentarily move off their positions. The fluctuation causes the node to momentarily move off its optimal position, at which time the system's flight controller recognizes this fluctuation in position and rectifies the displacement. All of this movement is best represented by a uniformly distribution, bounded by the maximum position displacement due to wind. Fig. 9 shows the effects of these position fluctuations on the estimator's accuracy. In this simulation, the formation takes its position as dictated by the two-stage scheme but due to wind, experiences minor position fluctuations. These positional fluctuations are modeled as a zero mean uniformly random variable. The accuracy of the two-stage scheme simulation results with fluctuating positions is based on the ensemble average of 1000 trials. As determined by (11) and (16), the position fluctuations have minimal effects on the end MLE accuracy. Fig. 9 shows only minor deviations (< 0.3 dB) in

Fig. 9. Comparison of the two-stage scheme on an airborne quadrotor network with positional fluctuations (dotted line) and without positional fluctuations (solid line).

accuracy due to positional fluctuations up to a standard deviation of 20 meters. Overall, this simulation indicates that the two-stage scheme with minor positions fluctuations (< 20 meters standard deviation) still out performs the random fixed formation case.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A two-staged geolocation scheme was introduced and compared to the random fixed formation case. This scheme utilizes a set of mobile sensor nodes to form a reconfigurable TDOA sensor network for the MLE of a target emitter's location. This scheme is able to provide optimal position

estimates independent of the emitter's bearing. Finally, its implementation on an airborne network was explored and showed to be viable despite its unsteady station keeping.

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